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Calorie and Amino Acid Composition of *Cucurbita pepo* and *Cucumis melo* Seeds

S. S. JOSHI and R. K. SHRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, Govt. College of Engg. and Tech., Raipur (M. P.)

and

S. S. NIGAM

Department of Chemistry, Saugar University, Saugar (M. P.)

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CUCURBITA pepo and *Cucumis melo* seeds are found to be rich in calorie, proteins and all protein bound essential amino acids except tryptophane.

Cucurbita pepo and *Cucumis melo* belong to the family "Cucurbitaceae". As described by Kirtikar and Basu¹, their fruit and mature seeds possess several medicinal properties. These seeds are used as nerve tonic. Because of little published information on the subject, high calorie and protein contents of these seeds, the nutritional characteristics of their protein isolates are investigated and reported in this communication.

Experimental

Proximate chemical composition was determined by standard methods²⁻³. The results are given in table 1.

TABLE 1—PROXIMATE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF *Cucurbita pepo* AND *Cucumis melo* SEEDS

SEEDS	Per 100 g. of edible portion						Calorie
	Mois- ture	Fats	Proteins	Fibre	Ash	Carbohydr- ates	
<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	8.4	49.2	26.2	0.5	4.2	11.6	655
<i>Cucumis melo</i>	7.2	48.7	30.6	0.5	5.3	7.6	640

The coarsely ground seeds were defatted with petroleum ether (B.P. 60-80°) and the seed meals were analysed for N-contents. The seed meals of *Cucurbita pepo* and *Cucumis melo* were found to contain 66.8 and 68.2 percent of proteins. The defatted seeds were repeatedly extracted with cold alkaline 10% brine for several hours and filtered. The filtrate, on adjustment of pH-value between 3.5-4.5, precipitated proteins in yields 21.8 and 21.6% respectively from *Cucurbita pepo* and *Cucumis melo* seeds respectively. Proteins were hydrolysed completely by refluxing with a mixture of 6N.HCl and 80% formic acid taken in 1:1 ratio by volume and the hydrolysate concentrated to syrupy consistency by evaporation which was vacuum desiccated⁴. The mass was then dissolved in 10% isopropanol and qualitatively analysed by uni and two dimensional circular and vertical paper (Whatman No 1) and cellulose thin layer chromatographic techniques⁵⁻¹¹ using (1) n-butanol: acetic acid: water (4:1:1.6); (2) pyridine: water (4:1); (3) n-butanol: pyridine:

TABLE 2—AMINO ACID COMPOSITION OF PROTEIN ISOLATES OF *Cucurbita pepo* AND *Cucumis melo* SEEDS

(Amino acid percentage expressed in g/16 g of nitrogen)

% of Amino acid	<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	<i>Cucumis melo</i>
<i>Indispensable</i>		
1. Lysine	6.14	4.63
1. Histidine	1.56	1.44
3. Threonine	7.2	6.4
4. Phenylalanine	6.02	7.40
5. Valine	9.0	9.8
6. Methionine	2.8	0.8
7. Tryptophane	0.3	0.4
8. Leucine and isoleucine	12.9	13.4
<i>Semi-Indispensable</i>		
9. Serine*	5.2	4.3
10. Glycine (indispensable for chicks)	8.4	8.1
11. Tyrosine †	4.2	1.42
12. Cystine ‡	0.4	0.6
13. Arginine (indispensable both for rats and chicks)	14	14.1
<i>Dispensable</i>		
14. Glutamic acid	10.2	11.8
15. Aspartic acid	6.2	8.2
16. Alanine	6.1	8.4
17. Proline §	0.8	0.5
18. γ -Amino butyric acid	Traces	Traces

Mean values of 10 determinations

- * Serine exerts sparing effect upon glycine.
 † Tyrosine exerts sparing effect upon phenylalanine.
 ‡ Cystine exerts sparing effect upon methionine.
 § Optical density measured at 440 nm.

water (1:1:1) and (4) phenol : water (3:1) as solvents and various specific spraying reagents^{1,2-12}. Butanol-acetic acid-water in combination with pyridine-water/butanol-pyridine-water/phenol-water were used as solvents for developing two dimensional chromatograms. For quantitative determinations, ninhydrin colours of individual amino acids of the two dimensionally developed chromatogram were estimated photometrically^{1,6} at 570 nm using a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20-Colorimeter. The results are given in Table 2.

A perusal of tables 1 & 2 revealed that the seeds of *Cucurbita pepo* and *Cucumis melo* are rich both in calorie and protein contents. Their proteins are rich in all essential amino acids particularly lysine, (phenylalanine + tyrosine), threonine, valine, (leucine and isoleucine) and (methionine + cystine) except tryptophane.

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Electroinitiated Post-polymerization of Methylmethacrylate using Sugar plus Acid as Supporting Electrolyte

ARUN K. SARKAR and SANTI R. PALIT

Department of Physical Chemistry,
Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science,
Jadavpur, Calcutta 700032, India.

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IF electric current is passed through a solution of sodium acetate containing methylmethacrylate (MMA) until the solution turns faintly hazy, a good yield of polymer can be obtained even after switching off the current at this stage, provided the system is allowed to stand undisturbed for a few hours¹. This is termed Post-polymerization. Not many electrolytes are known to be efficient post-polymerization initiators and just a handful have been lately discovered².

We present here a preliminary report of a few binary initiators of anodic post-polymerization of methyl methacrylate, the individual components having no such power. Some inorganic acids, however, do have some power of cathodic post-polymerization under certain conditions³, and dextrose has been used as a component of a redox initiator^{4,5}.

Results and Discussion

The experimental arrangement is more or less the same as described by Palit¹. The electrolyte used is a solution of HCl containing a sugar. The solution is electrolysed to produce a faint haziness; the current is then switched off and the system is left undisturbed for a day or so after which the post-polymer is collected. The initial haziness has to be just optimum; if it is too strong there is a tendency towards gelation during post-polymerization, more so for cane sugar than for glucose.

Effect of concentration of dextrose and HCl is shown in Table 1 from which it is concluded that a

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ACID AND DEXTROSE CONCENTRATION IN THE ELECTROINITIATED POST-POLYMERIZATION OF METHYL METHACRYLATE USING DEXTROSE/HCl AS ELECTROINITIATOR ELECTROLYTE

[MMA]=1% (v/v), current=1000 mA × 60 mins., Temperature=32.5°C, Post-polymerization time=24 hrs.		
Conc. of dextrose in (M) HCl=0.72 M	Post polymer yield(%)	[η] at 30°C
0.1	0.75	—
0.2	50.7	—
0.3	58.6	1.12
0.4	55.0	—
0.5	52.6	1.15
0.6	51.5	—
Conc. of HCl in (M) Dextrose=0.3 M		
0.60	36.8	0.95
0.72	58.6	1.12
0.84	63.5	1.28
1.20	73.7	insoluble gel